

A PERSPECTIVE ON COMPOSITES

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The history of man is, from one point of view, the history of the materials he has employed to control, ameliorate, or beautify his environment. Perhaps the very first materials ever used by our ancestors or their early cousins were the natural composites - wood and bone. It may seem cavalier to dismiss the millenia between protohistory and the 1960's of our era in a single sentence, but what we now categorize as advanced composite materials actually stem from the United States military requirements of that period.

The first tentative excursions into the field of exotic, man-made, high modulus materials were focused on developing strong boron filaments and incorporating these as reinforcements into composites for possible use in aircraft structures. Glass had been used in pressure vessels and solid rocket motor casings where hoop strength ratio was critical, but rigidity was a lesser requirement. Attempts to develop glass reinforced composites for structural purposes had been unsuccessful, largely because we were unable to make glass with a high elastic modulus that would result in a sufficiently rigid end-item composite.

By 1964, the United States had an intensive research and technology effort under way that was aimed at developing an industrial capability to manufacture boron filaments and their associated composites on a large scale and, hopefully, at a reasonable cost. Laboratory samples of boron had been produced with moduli of 60 million pounds per square inch and tensile strengths of some 400,000 pounds per square inch - but the costs were close to prohibitive, ranging up to \$3,000 per pound. The technological task was to determine whether these excellent boron filament properties could be obtained in commercial quantity production and, as importantly, whether the costs could be reduced toward the level of perhaps \$100 a pound. Some experimental quantities of carbon fiber were just becoming available at this period, but suffered from poor mechanical properties.

By 1968, we had seen some progress. We could rely on boron filaments retaining their properties when manufactured in industrial quantities. We could use boron composites routinely in many aerospace applications with at least the same confidence we had developed over a much longer period for structural alloys. It was clear we could use this class of boron-epoxy composites for many more applications than we had targeted five years earlier;

it was clear we had a competent new material that could find its way into capital items as well as expendables. The most revealing progress, however, was in the economics of filament production: the United States research and technology program had very carefully emphasized the potentials for expanding applications rather than a fixed end-item market; further, the United States research and technology program had involved the industry directly as performers rather than simply as recipients of packaged technology developed in-house by the Government. The result of future market incentives and a competitive industry drove filament prices down by a factor or ten, reaching some \$250 per pound, without impairing quality.

But even at \$250 per pound, boron filaments for composite use suggested selected high-cost applications rather than a basic revolution in materials for widespread use in our industrialized society. There seemed to be a cost threshold with boron that would keep the price relatively high; the success of composites to date, however, suggested that an ultimately cheaper filament had to be found and exploited if the composite competition with heavy and energy-consuming structural metal alloys was to find its full flowering.

While much of the United States research and development work had concentrated on boron, others in the U.S. and abroad had been pursuing alternate materials research. Boron technology seemed slightly ahead of other filaments in 1968, and therefore was the first to be reduced to practice and incorporated into operational United States military aircraft - primarily for control surfaces requiring very high stiffness to avoid flutter. We began to see rudders, slats, horizontal stabilizers, and air deflector doors being manufactured from boron-epoxy materials for flight service in aircraft such as the F-4, the C-5, and the F-111. These applications were very successful, and led to decisions to use various composites in production models of F-14, F-15, and F-18 aircraft. This production and service evaluation period brought composite technology to the forefront for aerospace uses. The cost question remained, however, and we had begun looking at possible alternatives to the successful boron-epoxy composites. Early British (and the United States) work on graphite as a reinforcing filament was by now gaining considerable momentum and offering a technical promise that could not be ignored; we found that early versions of graphite-epoxy composites suffered from very poor transverse tensile strength properties, but the challenge to work out these problems was well worth taking up since there were such important economic implications to success. Eventual prices of \$10 per pound for graphite fiber could be reliably forecast if production demands grew to high enough levels. Both civil and military R&D programs in the United States were busily investigating the possibilities of graphite-epoxy materials during the late '60's, and were developing a growing body of evidence that this materials was going to be a reliable, predictable, and inexpensive contender, not only for aerospace applications, but eventually for a much wider market. We were beginning to see non-aerospace consumer goods - such as sports equipment - take advantage of graphite-epoxy's unique properties; this was extraordinarily welcome to the high technology community because of its potential for lowering materials costs with increasing volume.

There were a few clouds on the horizon, nevertheless. In 1970, Rolls Royce decided to use a graphite-epoxy composite material for the fan blades of its new RB211 engine. This was one of the first serious commercial or production commitments to the use of graphite composites by the aerospace industry. The subsequent history is well-known: the particular graphite-epoxy fan blades designed for the RB211 were unable to withstand the impact loads imposed by bird ingestion without failing catastrophically. For reasons quite beyond the relatively narrow limits of material technology, the highly publicized RB211 problem had severe economic implications for both the engine manufacturer and the engine's primary purchaser. These economic issues redounded

to the discredit of advanced composites around the world; there was a noticeable decline in enthusiasm for the use of such materials through the industrial community. It is perhaps typical of new materials that they experience difficulties as they are introduced into new applications, and that many properly conservative commercial interests have little to gain from taking the necessarily higher economic risks associated with the early introduction and debugging of a new materials technology.

Recognizing both the economic dynamics at play within the industry and the outstanding technical and cost promises of advanced composites, United States Federal research continued unabated. A major joint study by NASA and the Air Force in 1972 laid out unemotionally the status of composite technology in light of the requirements of the 1980's. It became evident during this study, nicknamed "Composites Recast," that the major barriers to evolutionary expansion of material usage were those of cost and confidence. It was a question of confidence in material reliability and performance rather than any fundamental issues about the technology itself; there was a lack of particular data on manufacturing methodologies and life cycle costs. There was also the volume-sensitive graphite fiber cost factor to consider in light of possible non-aerospace demand. By this time it was evident that some additional Federal effort could make a difference of years in the general acceptance of advanced composites and of graphite-based materials in particular. Considerable expansion of Federal programs ensued, with emphasis on developing a mature manufacturing technology and on acquiring significant in-use experience - in our case, this was extended flight data on aircraft components. We believe this phase was extremely successful; a review of papers presented three years ago at the first International Conference on Composite Materials indicates both growing manufacturing competence and accumulation of important quanta of demonstration and service time. Confidence was growing; there were data available to support forecasts that the major structural fraction of aircraft in the next decades would be composite. Consumer product demand for graphite fiber had grown to the point it outstripped aerospace demand, with concomitant reductions in cost. The turning point had come, and advanced composites were firmly embedded in the fabric of our industrial society.

Let me hasten to point out something I am sure is well understood by this audience but bears repetition in any case: virtually no introduction of new materials of substances into what can be called the "economic ecology" of the twentieth century has been free of technical surprise. Such surprise is a fact of life; it is a basic responsibility of the research and technology community to anticipate, avoid, or ameliorate such surprise. The course of human history being what it is suggests that we are getting better - but we are not perfect. We have reached a point of identifying and working with that family of problems I will call the "known unknowns;" we are still being surprised from time to time by the "unknown unknowns." Beryllium has been tamed - after considerable effort. Magnesium alloys are now routinely found in automobile parts - after a period of flammability concerns. Certain titanium alloys were found to suffer from the disease of stress corrosion, and early high strength aluminum alloys were very susceptible to corrosion fatigue. High strength steels were found to be subject to hydrogen embrittlement. Careful research, technology improvements, and engineering control of material applications have reduced these other similar "unknown unknowns" to the category of understood material properties that can be routinely taken into account.

Advanced composites cannot be expected to undergo a substantively different evolutionary history, except perhaps that their success record to date appears outstanding in comparison with other, earlier introductions of new materials. The impact sensitivity of graphite composites noted earlier was a real problem, but one that now appears manageable in the case of engine fan blades by hybridizing, or using a number of different fiber types with the matrix.

Another problem recently identified - and which will be discussed in detail at other sessions of this conference - is the moisture effect, or the impact on composite mechanical properties of moisture penetrating the matrix and perhaps reducing component strength and durability; it appears today that this can be managed by the right combination of chemistry and engineering. Other problems may, during the process of material maturation, come to the surface and have to be dealt with serially; I, for one, expect such problems to arise - and to be dealt with satisfactorily. I see nothing on the horizon that permanently darkens the future of advanced composites as the next giant step in materials technology.

With that rather sweeping assertion of personal faith in a technology to which I have dedicated a considerable portion of my technical career as a backdrop, let me now go into a particular problem of our industrial ecology that has just recently come to the attention of the materials community.

Now in most cases when engineers and chemists talk about the problems of a new material they refer to something intrinsic, something dealing with the innate properties and behavior of the material itself in a particular application. In the case of graphite composites, however, the recently expressed concerns deal with matters quite extrinsic to the composite itself.

In the 1880's, Edison made carbon filaments from organic precursors to use as lamp filaments; carbon in filament form is a good conductor. In the early 1960's, the first high strength graphite fibers were produced by stressing precursor yarns during pyrolysis; the 10-fold increase in elastic modulus was accompanied by a significant increase in electrical and thermal conductivity along the fiber axis because of the fiber's ordered microstructure. This conductivity was regarded, in the world of composites applications, as an added characteristic without particular relevance to the structural properties being sought.

As carbon and graphite fibers became more common, however, it was discovered that they could interfere with unprotected electrical and electronic circuits. Reports of such incidents from fiber manufacturers here and abroad led the industry to issue warning notices and to label raw graphite fiber with warnings as to its electrical properties. It was becoming evident that this new fiber had to be treated with care or it could become a source of significant interference with in-plant electrical equipment.

The phenomenon of electrical interference from free graphite fibers released into the atmosphere even today is not well documented, and only limited test data exist at present. What we can say is that interference seems to begin when unprotected circuits are exposed to 10^4 to 10^7 fiber-seconds per cubic meter. Since graphite fiber is light - less than 2 grams per cubic centimeter - and since the typical fiber diameter is in the 10 micrometer range, atmospheric transport over long distances can be predicted. Settled fibers can also be easily resuspended by small agitations. Since a few grams contain millions of individual fibers, continuing release of graphite fibers into the environment could become a pervasive social and economic nuisance, or worse, in a society as dependent on electrical equipment as our own. When fibers, alone or in strands, settle on or across circuits, they can cause resistive loading, shorts, or electrical arcing. Further, they can carry high currents at low voltages, and are hard to destroy. And being small, they are also hard to detect.

During the early 1970's, the composites community was making major strides in developing and demonstrating new graphite-epoxy materials; the scattering of individuals who were aware of the fiber's electrical properties assumed that, once encapsulated and isolated in a structural matrix, there were no

further reasons to be concerned. In late 1975, however, the crash and subsequent burning of an Air Force fighter with many boron-epoxy composite parts provided the first physical evidence that fibers can be released from their matrix in such an accident. In that case, the fibers were boron, not graphite, but the principle was established and had to be investigated further. By the end of the following year, further tests had shown that graphite fibers could be accidentally released into our industrial ecology from burning composites, such as in waste disposal or in certain classes of accidents.

At the same time, the potential uses of graphite composites were expanding rapidly. It was already certain that composites offered the automotive industry an important alternative in meeting United States fuel economy standards for the 1980's and beyond, and that the energy efficient aircraft of the next generation could benefit enormously from the use of these materials. I would note that world production of graphite fiber in 1977 was estimated at only 300 tons, 75% of which was used in general industrial and consumer goods and the rest in military and aerospace applications. Future usage was expected to rise rapidly; depending upon the assumptions, ranges of up to 500,000 tons per year by 1990 were being projected.

Within the United States Government technical community there developed the conviction that means had to be found to retain the highly beneficial uses of graphite composites without inadvertently subjecting society to new and perhaps unacceptable risks. A six-months long interagency study under the auspices of the United States Office of Science and Technology Policy, just recently completed, examined the potential problems and possible United States responses thereto. The study drew on the experience and expertise of a wide group of Federal agencies and examined the situation with evenhanded concern for prudence and progress. The study's conclusions were reflected in a set of Presidential decisions announced in January of this year: First, information about the phenomenon was to be widely and authoritatively disseminated so that appropriate remedies and problem avoidance measures would be understood and implemented. Second, the opportunity for graphite fiber-related incidents was to be minimized and assistance was to be made available in the event they should occur. And third, a priority research and development effort was to attack the longer range questions of better understanding the potential hazards, defining protective measures that could be employed, preventing atmospheric fiber release, and modifying existing materials to avoid potential hazards.

Some nine Federal agencies have defined responsibilities within the framework of this action plan, and activities are under way in each. The National Aeronautics and Space Administration was assigned a major role in coordinating Federal R&D activity: more specifically, NASA has the responsibility for further analysis to define the true extent of the potential hazards posed by inadvertent graphite fiber releases, especially in the area of civil aviation, and for research on modified or alternative materials that reduce the probable hazards. Other agencies and departments are charged with environmental monitoring, assessment of protective measures, waste disposal methods, and safety standards.

NASA's current graphite composite R&D work is looking at such technological fixes as modified matrixes that do not release their fibers when burnt, at fibers that will burn at lower temperatures, and at coatings that will encapsulate fibers even when the matrix is removed. We are confident that R&D advances can significantly reduce the probability of hazardous fiber release from future composites. We are confident that simple and effective protective measures - such as filters, conformal coatings, and circuit design practices - can eliminate much of the problem. We are confident that even the questions of composite waste disposal, control, and recycling have reasonable technological solutions. We are confident, above all, that our recognition of and

attacks on the potential problems today have avoided what might otherwise have become an extraordinarily difficult problem in the near future.

During the remainder of this exciting international conference you will hear of the enormous advances that have taken place since 1975. You will see that early promise is turning rapidly into economic reality. You will recognize that we are at the point of revolutionizing our basic materials industry - and that these technologies are on an ascending spiral that may leave the "Age of Metal" behind, just as we have passed the "Age of Stone."

In closing, I would simply like to restate what we all know but sometimes forget: technological advances make their richest and most permanent contributions to human progress when fully understood in the total context of the civilization they are to serve. It is a responsibility of the technologist, rather than the regulator, to assure the benign introduction of his new products into society.